

Model Assessment of Potential and Barriers to the Development of Renewable Energy Communities at the National Level

Assessing the Potential of Energy Communities: A Comparison of Methodologies (Background Paper #3)

Date: 24 October 2022 (Version 2)
 Authors: Lars Holstenkamp, Christian Kriel (ECOLOG Institute for Social-Ecological Research and Education)

Contents

- 1 BACKGROUND 3
 - 1.1 The Mandate 3
 - 1.2 Definitions of Potentials 3
 - 1.3 Structure of the Background Paper 4
- 2 TYPOLOGY OF METHODOLOGIES 4
 - 2.1 Overview 4
 - 2.2 Sector Development Approaches 4
 - 2.3 Bottom-up Modelling Approaches 6
 - 2.4 Mixed Approaches 7
- 3 DATA INPUT 7
 - 3.1 Overview 7
 - 3.2 Energy Community Data and Development Pathways 8
 - 3.3 Technology Data 9
 - 3.4 Investment Data 9
 - 3.5 Financial Data 10
- 4 RECOMMENDATIONS 10
- REFERENCES 12

Figures

- Figure 1: Different Potential Definitions 3
- Figure 2: Assessment of the Potential – Summary of the Process 8

Tables

- Table 1: Simplified Typology of Methods Used within the Sector Development Approach 5
- Table 2: Overview of the Elements Used in the Assessment by Capener (2014) 5
- Table 3: Overview of UK Studies on Community Energy Potential Using a Sector Development Approach 6
- Table 4: Overview of Bottom-up Modelling Approaches towards Assessing Energy Community Potential 7

Abbreviations

Capex	capital expenditures	NPV	net present value
DECC	Department for Energy and Climate Change	P2P	peer-to-peer
EU	European Union	PV	photovoltaics
FiT	feed-in tariff	RED II	recast Renewable Energy Directive
IPS	Industrial and Provident Society	RES	renewable energy sources
Max	maximum	SME	small and medium-sized enterprise
Min	minimum	UK	United Kingdom
MS	member state		

Acknowledgements

This study was conducted by ECOLOG Institute on behalf of REScoop.eu and funded by the European Climate Foundation.

We thank Josh Roberts and Stavroula Pappa from REScoop.eu for helpful comments and suggestions to paper drafts. We take all responsibility for remaining mistakes.

Corresponding Author & Contact Details

Dr. Lars Holstenkamp
ECOLOG Institute for Social-Ecological Research and
Education
Wichernstraße 34, Entrance B
21335 Lüneburg
Germany
lars.holstenkamp@ecolog-institut.de

Persistent Identifier

doi:10.5281/zenodo.7301559

1 Background

1.1 The Mandate

In Art. 22 Sec. 3 of the recast Renewable Energy Directive (RED II), the European Union (EU) requests their member states (MS) to carry out an assessment of (existing barriers and) “the potential of development of renewable energy communities in their territories.” This mandate is not specified anywhere. However, assessments of potentials are widespread in the energy sector. As will be illustrated below, existing potential assessments for energy communities implicitly or explicitly build on those well-known methodologies.

1.2 Definitions of Potentials

Generally, a potential means “qualities that exist and can be developed” (Oxford University Press, 2022). In the case of energy communities, these “qualities” are physical and technical [energy], but also social [communities]. There is a vast amount of works that assess the potential of different renewable energy technologies, especially onshore wind energy (Enevoldsen et al., 2019; Höltinger et al., 2016; Hoogwijk et al., 2004; Jäger et al., 2016; Lu et al., 2009; McKenna et al., 2022; Rinne et al., 2018), but also rooftop solar photovoltaics (PV) (Bódis et al., 2019) or different variable renewable energies (Risch et al., 2022). In the literature on renewable energy potentials, different concepts are commonly used (see Figure 1), even if not necessarily in the same way by all authors. Theoretical or physical potential usually denotes the capacity that could be used or developed based on available energy sources. For the assessment of the geographical potential, authors take into account the area available for development – with various databases in the background (Risch et al., 2022) and consideration of different land-use constraints (Hoogwijk et al., 2004; Lu et al., 2009; Ryberg et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2012) or limits regarding distance to load centres, which are bridged by transmission capacities with related losses, costs and visibility effects (Silva Herran et al., 2016).

Figure 1: Different Potential Definitions

Theoretical and/or geographical potential function as starting point for deriving further concepts by subtracting a portion that is not realisable due to certain constraints (McKenna et al., 2020):

- These can be of technical nature, which leads to the technical, potential, i.e. the potential considering a given technology.
- We distinguish here between market and economic constraints, both of which add another side-condition that needs to be met – in the former case: expected returns being larger than a pre-defined profit target; in the latter case: social benefits being larger than social costs. Most authors do not distinguish between firm- or project-level (micro) perspective and social or economy-wide (macro) perspective. So, often what

we term “market potential” is called “economic potential,” e.g. in Hoogwijk et al. (2004) or McKenna et al. (2020).

- If further non-technical constraints such as public acceptance, market or organisational barriers are considered, the resultant quantity will usually be called the feasible potential.

These different potentials could be implemented by different actors, including energy communities. Hence, they form the upper limit of the energy community potential. Usually only a certain fraction of the economic or feasible potential is realised by energy communities.

Authors make various assumptions to calculate these different potentials. In this regard, we distinguish between hypothetical and implementable potential:

- Hypothetical potential means under reasonable external conditions realisable amount of energy community installations through beneficial policy measures (“best case” scenario).
- Implementable potential is the part of the hypothetical potential that seems realisable considering internal social and organisational constraints and likely policy pathways (“business-as-usual” scenario).

1.3 Structure of the Background Paper

Both implementable and hypothetical potential can be the result of an assessment of the energy community potential in an EU MS. Technical, market, economic or feasible potential usually build a starting point of the assessment, as will be shown below. We will not explain different methodologies to calculate these potentials, but concentrate on the “community” part here. Rather, we refer readers to the references cited above.

Several approaches have been developed in the literature so far to conduct assessments of energy community potentials. In the following, we

- analyse these approaches used (typology of methodologies, Section 2),
- give an overview of different model elements, parameters and estimation techniques used in existing studies (data input, Section 3) and,
- building on this comparison, propose alternative models as part of the model assessment template (recommendations, Section 4 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**).

2 Typology of Methodologies

2.1 Overview

Projections of energy community potential build either on extrapolations from existing energy community data and/or on hypothetical investment propensity. With regard to the modelling procedure, we distinguish two general approaches and a mixed one:

1. Pure extrapolation of energy community growth, using scenarios partly substantiated by a reflection of the institutional and technological environment and its development and/or some kind of more sophisticated time series analysis. We call this the “**sector development approach**”. It can focus on two different target quantities: projected installations and investment amounts from the community or the community share in overall investments.
2. Stated preferences, i.e. willingness to invest in energy communities, disposable income and some assumptions about the split of the investment portfolio combined with growth of renewable energies (or other technologies), cost projections and assumptions regarding financial structures. We call this the “**bottom-up modelling approach**”.
3. The previous approach can be combined with as much input as possible from energy community analyses. We call this a “**mixed approach**”. As we will show in the next two sections, the use of some energy community sector data in combination with a bottom-up modelling approach is the approach commonly applied in existing studies on energy community potentials.

Potential assessments for energy communities further differ according to their technology scope or group of actors included: Different from Capener (2014) and Laes et al. (2021), for instance, CE Delft (2016) includes small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and local authorities.

2.2 Sector Development Approaches

In general, this approach tries to forecast the future development of the energy community sector. In this way, an implementable potential is determined – a “potential” that is likely to be realised in the future. Hence, any forecasting method may be applied in this context (Armstrong, 2002; Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018; Ord et al., 2017):

qualitative or judgmental forecasting, if no historical data are available and/or adjustments are to be made, or quantitative, i.e. time series forecasting, if historical data are available – e.g. data from a monitoring system. The second requirement for the application of quantitative forecasting methods is that some aspects of past patterns will most reasonably continue into the future (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018). Forecasts can be built around the historical data of the target variable only (time series models) or include predictor variables, i.e. factors that explain developments of the target variable (explanatory models), or both (mixed models) (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018). Assessments of barriers and drivers, for instance, may be used to identify constraints on hypothetical potentials to be realised. These factors might be integrated into a forecasting model. Lastly, forecasts can lead to a single prediction of the future development or a set of predictions (forecast distribution) (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018). In the following, we use a simplified typology of time series analysis vs. judgemental forecasting, specifically trend continuation vs. scenario approach as a first dimension to distinguish methods to assess the potential. Time series analysis requires an existing monitoring system or historical data on energy communities, respectively. Ideally, longer time series are available, so that certain patterns and predictor variables can be identified. If none, or not enough, historical data are available, a judgemental forecasting method such as scenario forecasting seems appropriate (see Section 3.2 below).

The second dimension relates to the quantity targeted with forecasting. Assessors of energy community potential could use either installed capacities or amounts of investments by energy communities or shares of energy communities in total installed capacities or investments, reasonably separated by renewable energy technology. (For business areas other than electricity or heat generation, another suitable indicator/quantity must be determined). In the latter case, shares need to be multiplied with market size, i.e. forecast or potential of the respective technology in the jurisdiction under investigation (see Section 3.3 below).

Our simplified typology with two dimensions and two values each leads to a 2x2 matrix of possible determination methods within the Sector Development Approach as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Simplified Typology of Methods Used within the Sector Development Approach

	Times Series Analysis	Judgemental Forecasting
Installed Capacities Amount of Investments	Extrapolation of Installed Capacities/Investments (A)	Scenarios of Installed Capacities/Investments (B)
Shares in Total Installed Capacities Shares in Total Investments	Extrapolation of Shares (C)	Scenarios of Shares (D)

The study for the United Kingdom (UK) by Capener (2014) generally follows a sector-development approach. He uses historical data on growth (start-ups per year), success rates, average number of members and average investment per member per initial share offer and follow-on share offers to calculate community investments. Considering the typical financial structure leads to total investments by energy communities. Using specific investment costs per technology, this quantity can be translated into installed capacities (newly/annually and accumulated total). If total/newly installed capacity is known/forecasted or potential estimated, the community share can be calculated. Capener (2014) amends historical growth rates using expert opinions and builds three scenarios: high, medium and low.

Table 2: Overview of the Elements Used in the Assessment by Capener (2014)

Target Quantity	Element	Forecasting Method	Data Source
Community investment	Growth rates (number of start-ups)	"Current trends", partly not explicated Judgmental: scenarios	Historical data, IPS only Expert opinion?
	Success rate		
	Number of members per share offer		
	Investment per member		
	Numbers for follow-on share offers		
Community capacity	Specific investment costs (Capex by technology & size class)	Simulations?	FIT Review
Community share	Total investment/capacity		

Abbreviations: Capex: capital expenditures; FIT: Feed-in tariff; IPS: Industrial and Provident Society

Overall, data demand is relatively high as quite specific data are needed (see Table 2), especially membership data by investment opportunity, investment per member and financial structures of energy communities, ideally per technology as these can vary significantly. If number of members per share offer and overall investments are known, the average investment per member can be calculated – for single projects/offers/initiatives and the whole population. Alternatively, surveys among members would be needed.

Other examples of potential assessments building on energy community sector data are studies by SCENE Consult for ResPublica (Harnmeijer et al., 2013) and by WPI Economics (Edgar et al., 2020), all for the UK (see Table 3). The latter check plausibility of forecasts using historical data for the UK and international experience from “front-runner countries” Denmark and Germany with high community energy penetration.

Table 3: Overview of UK Studies on Community Energy Potential Using a Sector Development Approach

Authors	Target Quantity	Target Year	Main Forecasting Approach
Camco and Baker Tilly (2011)	Installed capacity	2020	Geographical extrapolation (Cambridgeshire to whole of UK)
Harnmeijer et al. (2013)	Installed capacity Community share	2020 2020	Extrapolation (exponential) Camco and Baker Tilly (2011), extrapolated across ownership structures (naïve forecast/constant, 2013) x DECC estimates
Capener (2014)	Sector growth (number of start-ups/ investment)	2020	Scenarios
Edgar et al. (2020)	Sector growth (installed capacity)	2030	Scenarios: - Low: naïve forecast/constant (2018 growth rate) - Medium: taken from Capener (2014) - High: taken from Harnmeijer et al. (2013) Plausibility check using international experience

Abbreviations: DECC: Department for Energy and Climate Change

2.3 Bottom-up Modelling Approaches

Bottom-up modelling approaches attempt to identify hypothetical potentials of energy communities – expressed as number of households involved (CE DELFT, 2016), share in total investments (Laes et al., 2021; Pons-Seres de Brauwer & Cohen, 2020), installed capacity (Fina et al., 2020, 2022) or amount of community investments (Pons-Seres de Brauwer & Cohen, 2020) – in the jurisdiction under investigation. As the assessment studies chosen here for the comparison illustrate (see Table 4), there are various ways to arrive at those target quantities. Authors either focus on investment behavior as in the case of Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen (2020), but generally also in CE Delft (2016) and Laes et al. (2021), or on modelling of the technical and economic potential as in Fina et al. (2020, 2022). While Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen (2020) investigate hypothetical investments, CE Delft (2016) and Laes et al. (2021) combine technology data with hypothetical investments (abilities-to-invest and/or willingness-to-invest), including assumptions on financial data to transform technological quantities into monetary ones (investment projections). Fina et al. (2020, 2022) rather determine a technical-economic potential of energy communities without further consideration of investment behaviour, willingness- or ability-to-invest. A similar approach has been developed, for instance, for calculating the energy sharing potential in Germany (Wiesenthal et al., 2022).

The list of factors included in different bottom-up modelling approaches indicates that many assumptions have to be made on the way to the final value for the potential – principally at all steps of the analysis. Point estimates of the potential must therefore be viewed rather critically. At best, authors present a sensitivity analysis of critical model parameters. At the very least, the effects of the choice of parameters should be briefly described.

Table 4: Overview of Bottom-up Modelling Approaches towards Assessing Energy Community Potential

Authors	Actor Focus	Technology Focus	Target Quantity (Target Year)	Modelling Techniques
CE Delft (2016)	individuals/ privH, collec- tives, public en- tities, SMEs	Wind onshore PV Stationary bat- teries, electric boilers, EVs	Number of households (2030, 2050)	Total installations: - Technical potential, Greenpeace Energy Revolution scenario Propensity to invest: - Willingness-to-invest estimates (number of households) - Normalized average savings rate x min or max annual investment Number of households per technology deduplicated \Rightarrow number of house- holds with any technology
Laes et al. (2021)	privH	Wind onshore PV (ground- mounted, roof- top)	Community share (2030)	Total installations: - Technical potential (bottom-up modelling) - Political potential: political targets (regional or national downscaled to regional level) Total RES investments = total in- stalled capacity x Capex Community equity investments: - max: fraction of annual household disposable income (2% min, 4% max) - expected: propensity to invest (sur- veys, trend analysis, other assump- tions = proxies) - Technology split according to needed/projected capacities Community investments = equity in- vestments / equity ratio (scenarios: 100% vs. 20%)
Fina et al. (2020, 2022)	privH ("build- ings"), P2P	Rooftop PV	Installed capac- ity	Geographical & technical potential Economic potential: NPV optimisation
Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen (2020)	individuals	Wind onshore (Solar PV)	Community investment	Capital requirement x probability to in- vest (choice experiment) x population (aged 25-64)

Abbreviations: EVs: electric vehicles; max: maximum; min: minimum; NPV: net present value; P2P: peer-to-peer, privH: private households, PV: photovoltaics; RES: renewable energy sources

2.4 Mixed Approaches

Several variables and parameters used in bottom-up modelling approaches can principally be compared and substituted with actual (i.e. historical) or projected data (i.e. forecasts) from sector development approaches. The resultant methodology is a mixed approach combining bottom-up modelling with parameter input from energy community sector data. The bottom-up modelling approaches listed in the previous section partly follow such a strategy for some model parameters, e.g. CE Delft (2016) regarding technology split or Laes et al. (2021) with regard to the propensity to invest, where it is derived from actual community investment (but not applied in model regions).

3 Data Input

3.1 Overview

The assessment process starts with the selection of the modelling approach and a collection of input data. The "sector development approach" needs energy community data (or expert judgements of these) – if possible, in high resolution. If a monitoring system is in place, data could be drawn from this (see Figure 2).

A “bottom-up modelling approach” relies on data of different nature and from different sources. We group them into “investment data”, “technology data” and “financial data” and describe them in more details in the following sections. The former include disposable income or wealth and population/household data, which can be taken from official statistics, data on willingness-to-invest from surveys and/or choice experiments and on asset allocation in private households’, SMEs’ and local authorities’ portfolios. Projections of future installations at a certain point in time or over a certain period are usually taken from external sources – model scenarios, policy targets or physical/technical potentials. Installed capacities are then translated into monetary units by dividing them through cost projections. Since private households, SMEs and local authorities usually combine equity that they invest into these projects with other forms of financing and sometimes co-invest with other actors, further assumptions regarding financing conditions and ownership structures are needed.

Figure 2: Assessment of the Potential – Summary of the Process

3.2 Energy Community Data and Development Pathways

As the UK studies described in Section 2.2 illustrate, sector development approaches usually start with some available energy community data, extrapolate from these and often include some expert judgement to construct more or less plausible scenarios. If many data are available, e.g. from a monitoring system, and long time series of observations, and if it is likely that patterns identifiable from those time series will last into the future, standard times series methods to forecasting may be applied. Depending on the concrete approach developed, such data may include:

- development of the number of energy communities,
- numbers of members and installed capacities,
- ideally differentiated (a) according to type of actor (private households, local authorities, SMEs), (b) technology (especially wind, rooftop/small PV, ground-mounted/large PV, biomass, storage, heating, EVs) and (c) geographically into different regions.

Forecasts based on time series model probable future outcomes providing that past patterns persist in the future. Hence, two of the UK studies include judgmental forecasts in the form of expert opinion (Capener, 2014) or past studies (Edgar et al., 2020) in the form of different scenarios. In the ideal case, an assessment of potentials would combine the participative assessment of barriers and challenges with questions on scenarios and potential developments of the energy community sector.

3.3 Technology Data

Principally, there are two different ways how to identify the capacity of renewable energy installations (Laes et al., 2021):

1. **Scenario approaches** based on past developments, simulations or policy targets and
2. Assessments of the (physical, geographical, technical, market/economic and/or feasible) **potential** as outlined in Section 1.2.

Using policy targets would be consistent with a policy evaluation perspective that is generally taken in the assessment of energy community potentials. However, sometimes targets do not exist or are not very ambitious. In the latter case, this could lead to lower estimations of energy community potentials if a fixed share for energy communities is used as in the case of Camco and Baker Tilly (2011), or to an overestimation of the energy community share likely to be realised. Alternatively, time series on past installations and model simulations are widely available for all countries.

If the second option is taken, i.e. an assessment of technology potential, the right concept needs to be selected with care as assumptions made in this regard may clash with other assumptions underlying the choice of other parameters/model elements and different elements in the system interact. This is especially true for market/economic and feasible potential: Community ownership most likely increases, all else being equal, project-related social acceptance (Musall & Kuik, 2011; Warren & McFadyen, 2010) – and therefore enlarges the feasible potential if acceptance constraints are included to calculate this quantity.

3.4 Investment Data

Assessment studies usually use an “average”, “typical” or “representative” household or individual and extrapolate to the whole population able and willing to invest. The assessments start at different points to calculate hypothetical investments. Overall, data needed can be grouped under the following categories:

- a) The number of households or individuals that are to be considered (“population”)
- b) The share of households or individuals willing to invest (“stated preferences”) or the share of those invested (“market observations”)
- c) Investment amounts per household or individual or disposable income or wealth and savings rates
- d) Information about the asset allocation, i.e. on the portfolio of households

Population or household data can be taken from official statistics. Assumptions need to be made, though, about that part of the population, which is allowed and able or likely to invest. Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen (2020), for instance, take all people aged 25-64. However, surveys among members of community energy groups illustrate that there are, of course, also younger and older members (Bauwens, 2016; Holstenkamp & Kahla, 2016; Radtke, 2016). We do not know of any data on the number of household members usually engaged in energy communities. But while it is most probably only a single member representing the whole household in many cases, there is at least anecdotal evidence of families with several members in energy community companies. Hence, both individuals and households can be used as basis to extrapolate investment potential. Lastly, any assessment of future potentials need to consider demographic changes. The number of inhabitants of a jurisdiction (and its composition) will change. Usually, a fixed number from a (more or less arbitrarily) chosen year. Laes et al. (2021) take the average for 2020 to 2030. However, any population forecast is highly uncertain. Assessments should therefore at least consider different projections.

With the exception of Fina et al. (2020, 2022), the bottom-up modelling approaches referred to above all use willingness-to-invest data to restrict investors to a part of the total population. Data are usually taken from surveys (Laes et al., 2021) or experimental studies (Pons-Seres de Brauwer & Cohen, 2020), even if the approach is principally open for including data on actual investments by citizens, SMEs and local authorities. Pure market observations will certainly reflect existing conditions and therefore underestimate the potential. Stated preference approaches, on the other hand, may overestimate the feasible potential. However, a more detailed micro modelling of investment behaviour, e.g. based on known influencing factors, increases data demands. The propensity to invest can be derived from stated preferences studies on RES investments in general or energy community investments specifically. Besides the Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen (2020) article, which includes observations from all EU MSs, and an article by Wu et al. (2022) on ten different EU MSs, there are various studies available, for instance, for Austria and Switzerland (Ebers Broughel & Hampl, 2018), Belgium/Flanders (Conradie et al., 2021), France (Bourcet & Bovari, 2020), Germany (Fischer et al., 2021; Kalkbrenner & Roosen, 2016; Salm et al., 2016) and Ireland (Curtin et al., 2019). All studies cited here concentrate on private individuals or households. There are fewer studies on SMEs and public authorities.

As demographic data, disposable income or wealth data can be taken from official statistics. These should be available for private households as well as SMEs and local authorities. Actual investments in energy communities per member can be taken from surveys (Bauwens, 2019; Holstenkamp & Kahla, 2016).

Depending on the concrete model, further assumptions may need to be made regarding the allocation of investments between (community) renewables and other investments and/or within renewable investments, e.g. wind energy vs. solar PV. For the latter, CE Delft (2016), for instance, takes known data for the Netherlands and France as default value. Technology preferences vary from country to country, though (Pons-Seres de Brauwer & Cohen, 2020; Wu et al., 2022). Therefore, we see such an assumption rather critically.

3.5 Financial Data

This category of input data needed especially for bottom-up modelling approaches, comprises:

- data on specific costs of installations,
- information about financial structures and
- implicit or explicit assumptions regarding ownership structures.

Installed capacities need to be translated into monetary units and investment potentials into potential installed capacities. This can be done using specific costs for the different technologies. Market data are generally available for different segments (i.e. installation sizes), even if not necessarily for energy communities specifically. Moreover, methods to forecast future costs, e.g. through “learning curves”, are well-established (and potential limitations well known) (Görig & Breyer, 2016; Grübler et al., 1999; Neij et al., 2003; Nemet, 2006).

Since private households, SMEs and local authorities usually combine equity that they invest into these projects with other forms of financing and sometimes co-invest with other actors, further assumptions regarding financing conditions and ownership structures are needed. These could build on market data for those technologies under investigation, on specific energy community data or on expert interviews. While the first two options would mean to extrapolate past data into the future, the latter option could include experts’ expectations of future developments regarding financial structures.

Financial structures for renewable energy projects differ across countries, technologies, segments and project sponsors. Some data on financial structures are available (Đukan & Kitzing, 2021; Holstenkamp, 2019; Roth et al., 2022). Typically, larger-scale wind energy and ground-mounted PV projects are financed using industry standards for utility-scale installations. In this case, equity ratios or financial structures in general should approximate market averages. However, this also depends on the type of the financial system in the country under investigation (Holstenkamp, L. et al., 2020). Smaller PV installations are partly financed using equity only, i.e. with an equity ratio of 100% (Holstenkamp et al., 2018). Therefore, in our opinion, a differentiation by segment is necessary.

Joint ventures of project developers and other commercial players with energy communities or other forms of shared ownership are known from different countries (Goedkoop & Devine-Wright, 2016; Harnmeijer et al., 2013; Kahla et al., 2017). Harnmeijer et al. (2013) fully count them into the energy community sector. In that case, they “multiply” the energy community potential, measured in total investments and installed capacities, in a similar way as smaller equity ratios. Unless detailed sector data are available, it is difficult, though, to estimate the share of joint undertakings.

4 Recommendations

We do not recommend a specific modelling approach. Rather, we think that the selection of the approach highly depends on data availability and purpose. Ideally, assessments of potential using different approaches can be compared and a range of likely values for implementable and hypothetical potentials be given.

This said, we first recommend to collect input data in a structured way to be able to meaningfully compare assessment results from different models. As relevant parameters in bottom-up modelling approaches come from surveys and/or choice experiments, these are likely candidates for such a collection of potential input data. We think that these could be translated into default values for selected parameters in these bottom-up modelling approaches.

Secondly, we recommend to improve data availability regarding energy community data, e.g. by establishing monitoring systems or other forms of standardised data collections. These feed into sector development approaches as well as bottom-up modelling approaches. Moreover, this will improve the quality of assessments.

Thirdly, a simplified model such as the framework of Laes et al. (2021) seems to us to be a good candidate for a “standard” that offers sufficient scope for adaptation to data availability and framework conditions in a given region. We recommend to use such a kind of model with country- (or even region-)specific data wherever possible – ideally together with a simplified sector development approach building on extrapolations of community investments.

Fourthly, consistency within modelling approaches, especially with regard to scenarios used, is challenging. We therefore recommend to explicate underlying assumptions for all modelling elements. Pathways constructed using the “sector development approach” should be checked against results from the assessment of barriers and drivers.

References

- Armstrong, J. S. (Ed.). (2002). *Principles of forecasting: A handbook for researchers and practitioners* (7th ed.). Kluwer.
- Bauwens, T. (2016). Explaining the diversity of motivations behind community renewable energy. *Energy Policy*, 93, 278–290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.03.017>
- Bauwens, T. (2019). Analyzing the determinants of the size of investments by community renewable energy members: Findings and policy implications from Flanders. *Energy Policy*, 129, 841–852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.02.067>
- Bódis, K., Kougias, I., Jäger-Waldau, A., Taylor, N., & Szabó, S. (2019). A high-resolution geospatial assessment of the rooftop solar photovoltaic potential in the European Union. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 114, 109309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109309>
- Bourcet, C., & Bovari, E. (2020). Exploring citizens' decision to crowdfund renewable energy projects: Quantitative evidence from France. *Energy Economics*, 88, 104754. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2020.104754>
- Camco, & Baker Tilly. (2011). *The Potential for the GIB to Support Community Renewables* (Quoted from Harnmeijer et al. (2013)).
- Capener, P. (2014). *Community Renewable Electricity Generation: Potential Sector Growth to 2020—Methodology, Detailed Assumptions and Summary of Results, FINAL REPORT*.
- CE DELFT. (2016). *The potential of energy citizens in the European Union*.
- Conradie, P. D., De Ruyck, O., Saldien, J., & Ponnet, K. (2021). Who wants to join a renewable energy community in Flanders? Applying an extended model of Theory of Planned Behaviour to understand intent to participate. *Energy Policy*, 151, 112121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.112121>
- Curtin, J., McInerney, C., Gallachóir, B. Ó., & Salm, S. (2019). Energizing local communities—What motivates Irish citizens to invest in distributed renewables? *Energy Research & Social Science*, 48, 177–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.08.020>
- Đukan, M., & Kitzing, L. (2021). The impact of auctions on financing conditions and cost of capital for wind energy projects. *Energy Policy*, 152, 112197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112197>
- Ebers Broughel, A., & Hampl, N. (2018). Community financing of renewable energy projects in Austria and Switzerland: Profiles of potential investors. *Energy Policy*, 123, 722–736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.08.054>
- Edgar, J., Ahern, J., & Williams, M. (2020). *The future of community energy—A WPI Economics report for SP Energy Networks*. WPI Economics. <https://wpieconomics.com/site/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Future-of-Community-Energy-20200129-Web-Spreads.pdf>
- Enevoldsen, P., Permién, F.-H., Bakhtaoui, I., Krauland, A.-K. von, Jacobson, M. Z., Xydis, G., Sovacool, B. K., Valentine, S. V., Luecht, D., & Oxley, G. (2019). How much wind power potential does Europe have? Examining European wind power potential with an enhanced socio-technical atlas. *Energy Policy*, 132, 1092–1100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.06.064>
- Fina, B., Auer, H., & Friedl, W. (2020). Cost-optimal economic potential of shared rooftop PV in energy communities: Evidence from Austria. *Renewable Energy*, 152, 217–228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.01.031>
- Fina, B., Monsberger, C., & Auer, H. (2022). A framework to estimate the large-scale impacts of energy community roll-out. *Heliyon*, 8(7), e09905. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09905>
- Fischer, B., Gutsche, G., & Wetzels, H. (2021). Who wants to get involved? Determining citizen willingness to participate in German renewable energy cooperatives. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 76, 102013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102013>
- Goedkoop, F., & Devine-Wright, P. (2016). Partnership or placation? The role of trust and justice in the shared ownership of renewable energy projects. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 17, 135–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2016.04.021>
- Görig, M., & Breyer, C. (2016). Energy learning curves of PV systems. *Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy*, 35(3), 914–923. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ep.12340>
- Grübler, A., Nakićenović, N., & Victor, D. G. (1999). Dynamics of energy technologies and global change. *Energy Policy*, 27(5), 247–280. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-4215\(98\)00067-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-4215(98)00067-6)
- Harnmeijer, J., Parsons, M., & Julian, C. (2013). *The Community Renewables Economy—Starting up, scaling up and spinning out*. ResPublica. https://www.respublica.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2013/09/yqq_Community-Renewables-Economy.pdf
- Holstenkamp, L. (2019). Financing Consumer (Co-)Ownership of Renewable Energy Sources. In J. Lowitzsch (Ed.), *Energy Transition*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Holstenkamp, L., Becker, T., Beigang, A., Ehrtmann, M., Davis, M., Brown, D., & Hall, S. (2020). *Stakeholder Report on Financial Innovation for Prosumer Expansion* (D4.3; Version 2, PROSEU - Prosumers for the Energy Union: Mainstreaming Active Participation of Citizens in the Energy Transition). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/record/4115688>
- Holstenkamp, L., & Kahla, F. (2016). What are community energy companies trying to accomplish? An empirical investigation of investment motives in the German case. *Energy Policy*, 97, 112–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.07.010>
- Holstenkamp, L., Kahla, F., & Degenhart, H. (2018). Finanzwirtschaftliche Annäherungen an das Phänomen Bürgerbeteiligung. In L. Holstenkamp & J. Radtke (Eds.), *Handbuch Energiewende und Partizipation* (pp. 281–301). Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-09416-4_17
- Höltlinger, S., Salak, B., Schuppenlehner, T., Scherhauer, P., & Schmidt, J. (2016). Austria's wind energy potential – A participatory modeling approach to assess socio-political and market acceptance. *Energy Policy*, 98, 49–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.08.010>

- Hoogwijk, M., de Vries, B., & Turkenburg, W. (2004). Assessment of the global and regional geographical, technical and economic potential of onshore wind energy. *Energy Economics*, 26(5), 889–919. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2004.04.016>
- Hyndman, R. J., & Athanasopoulos, G. (2018). *Forecasting: Principles and practice* (2nd ed.). OTexts.
- Jäger, T., McKenna, R., & Fichtner, W. (2016). The feasible onshore wind energy potential in Baden-Württemberg: A bottom-up methodology considering socio-economic constraints. *Renewable Energy*, 96, 662–675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2016.05.013>
- Kahla, F., Holstenkamp, L., Müller, J. R., & Degenhart, H. (2017). *Entwicklung und Stand von Bürgerenergiegesellschaften und Energiegenossenschaften in Deutschland*. Leuphana Universität Lüneburg (Leuphana), Institut für Bank-, Finanz- und Rechnungswesen. http://www.leuphana.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Forschungseinrichtungen/professuren/finanzierung-finanzwirtschaft/files/Arbeitspapiere/wpbl27_BEG-Stand_Entwicklungen.pdf
- Kalkbrenner, B. J., & Roosen, J. (2016). Citizens' willingness to participate in local renewable energy projects: The role of community and trust in Germany. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 13, 60–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.12.006>
- Laes, E., Anfinson, K., Krug, M., Gatta, V., Meynaerts, E., De Luca, E., Cotroneo, R., Caliano, M., Klävs, G., Kudrenickis, I., Aakre, S., Håkon, S., Standal, K., Nowakowski, P., Wnuk, R., Azevedo, I., & Maleki, P. (2021). *Deliverable 2.2—Assessment report of potentials for RES community energy in the target regions*. COME RES. https://come-res.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Resources/Deliverables/COME_RES_Deliverable_WP4.1_Organisational_and_Legal_Forms_and_Business_Models.pdf
- Lu, X., McElroy, M. B., & Kiviluoma, J. (2009). Global potential for wind-generated electricity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(27), 10933–10938. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0904101106>
- McKenna, R., Pfenninger, S., Heinrichs, H., Schmidt, J., Staffell, I., Bauer, C., Gruber, K., Hahmann, A. N., Jansen, M., Klingler, M., Landwehr, N., Larsén, X. G., Lilliestam, J., Pickering, B., Robinius, M., Tröndle, T., Turkovska, O., Wehrle, S., Weinand, J. M., & Wohland, J. (2022). High-resolution large-scale onshore wind energy assessments: A review of potential definitions, methodologies and future research needs. *Renewable Energy*, 182, 659–684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.10.027>
- McKenna, R., Ryberg, D. S., Staffell, I., Hahmann, A. N., Schmidt, J., Heinrichs, H., Höltinger, S., Lilliestam, J., Pfenninger, S., Robinius, M., Stolten, D., Tröndle, T., Wehrle, S., & Weinand, J. M. (2020). On the socio-technical potential for onshore wind in Europe: A response to Enevoldsen et al. (2019), *Energy Policy*, 132, 1092–1100. *Energy Policy*, 145, 111693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111693>
- Musall, F. D., & Kuik, O. (2011). Local acceptance of renewable energy—A case study from southeast Germany. *Energy Policy*, 39(6), 3252–3260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.03.017>
- Neij, L., Andersen, P. D., & Durstewitz, M. (2003). The use of experience curves for assessing energy policy programs. *Proceedings of the EU/IEA Workshop on Experience Curves: A Tool for Energy Policy Analysis and Design*, 3–14.
- Nemet, G. F. (2006). Beyond the learning curve: Factors influencing cost reductions in photovoltaics. *Energy Policy*, 34(17), 3218–3232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2005.06.020>
- Ord, J. K., Fildes, R., & Kourentzes, N. (2017). *Principles of business forecasting* (2nd ed.). Wessex Press, Inc. Oxford University Press. (2022). *Potential (noun)*. Oxford Learner's Dictionaries. https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/potential_2
- Pons-Seres de Brauwer, C., & Cohen, J. J. (2020). Analysing the potential of citizen-financed community renewable energy to drive Europe's low-carbon energy transition. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 133, 110300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110300>
- Radtke, J. (2016). *Bürgerenergie in Deutschland*. Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-14626-9>
- Rinne, E., Holttinen, H., Kiviluoma, J., & Rissanen, S. (2018). Effects of turbine technology and land use on wind power resource potential. *Nature Energy*, 3(6), 494–500. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-018-0137-9>
- Risch, S., Maier, R., Du, J., Pflugradt, N., Stenzel, P., Kotzur, L., & Stolten, D. (2022). Potentials of Renewable Energy Sources in Germany and the Influence of Land Use Datasets. *Energies*, 15(15), 5536. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15155536>
- Roth, A., Đukan, M., Anatolitis, V., Jimeno, M., Banasiak, J., Brückmann, R., & Kitzing, L. (2022). *Financing conditions of renewable energy projects – results from an EU wide survey* (p. 136). <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/1-136/v2>
- Ryberg, D., Robinius, M., & Stolten, D. (2018). Evaluating Land Eligibility Constraints of Renewable Energy Sources in Europe. *Energies*, 11(5), 1246. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11051246>
- Salm, S., Hille, S. L., & Wüstenhagen, R. (2016). What are retail investors' risk-return preferences towards renewable energy projects? A choice experiment in Germany. *Energy Policy*, 97, 310–320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.07.042>
- Silva Herran, D., Dai, H., Fujimori, S., & Masui, T. (2016). Global assessment of onshore wind power resources considering the distance to urban areas. *Energy Policy*, 91, 75–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2015.12.024>
- Warren, C. R., & McFadyen, M. (2010). Does community ownership affect public attitudes to wind energy? A case study from south-west Scotland. *Land Use Policy*, 27(2), 204–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2008.12.010>

- Wiesenthal, J., Aretz, A., Ouanes, N., & Petrick, K. (2022). *Energy Sharing: Eine Potenzialanalyse. Gemeinschaftlich Strom im Verteilnetz erzeugen und nutzen: Eine Studie zum Umsetzungsvorschlag im Rahmen von Artikel 22 der Erneuerbare-Energien-Richtlinie der EU*. Institut für ökologische Wirtschaftsforschung. https://www.ioew.de/fileadmin/user_upload/BILDER_und_Downloaddateien/Publikationen/2022/Energy_Sharing_Eine_Potenzialanalyse_1.pdf
- Wu, H., Carroll, J., & Denny, E. (2022). Harnessing citizen investment in community-based energy initiatives: A discrete choice experiment across ten European countries. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 89, 102552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102552>
- Zhou, Y., Luckow, P., Smith, S. J., & Clarke, L. (2012). Evaluation of Global Onshore Wind Energy Potential and Generation Costs. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 46(14), 7857–7864. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es204706m>